

Strategy Enhancement Sale On Msmes Roadside Stall Sweet Pioneer In Makassar

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ABSTRACT

The economic conditions of society due to the Covid 19 pandemic have brought about very significant impact, especially for MSMEs the only one is Warung Manis Perintis. This business operates in the field culinary, this business began to experience a decline in sales of 65%. Problem in study This is How strategy Which should applied and How alternative strategy Which must prioritized in its implementation in this business. The method used For prioritize strategy marketing that is Analysis SWOT and QSPM (*Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix*). The purpose of this research is For determine strategy Which appropriate For increase sale And determine form alternative strategybased on Internal And External Matrix, And *Quantitative StrategicAppropriate Planning Matrix (QSPM) to be implemented*. Based on the results calculation BAG on analysis QSPM, obtained alternative First WhichThe most prioritized is the procurement of a variety of flavors and new types of products next with make packaging Which interesting so that sale Roadside stall Sweet Pioneers can increase.

Keywords: Business Strategy, SWOT Analysis, SWOT Matrix, Sales, Analysis Q.

INTRODUCTION

In today's industrial world this, every business owner sued for always give the best to its customers. Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) or Business Micro Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) have an important role in economic development of a country. Based on data submitted by the AuthorityService Finance (OJK) on month August 2021, MSMEs is bone back of the Indonesian economy by contributing 57.14 percent or equivalent Rp. 7,034.1 trillion from GDP Indonesia, with total moment This there is 65.5 Million perpetrator MSMEs And absorb 119.6 million person or 96.92 percent from total workforce.

Considering the very important and crucial role of MSMEs as one support economy, para perpetrator MSMEs must Can show quality Goodin terms of products, promotions and human resources. There are many stories business Which forced roll mat only Because not enough notice matter the.For can increase MSMEs through strategy enhancement sale, MSMEsIt is necessary to recognize the strengths and weaknesses of the business. This would be very help MSMEs recognize their own business conditions and take advantage of themevery opportunity that exists and avoid or minimize every threat from environment external.

Based on data from Ministry of Industry state that Indonesia need at least 4 million businessman new For join in in strengthening structureconomy. Plus data from BPS, ratio amount businessman in Indonesia Still as big as 3.4% or only around 9 million people of the total population. In the middle change environment business And competition business national nor international Which the more strict, Business Micro, Small And Intermediate (UMKM) moment This experiencecondition Which Enough difficult. MSMEs as Wrong One supporter growthThe economy, especially in Indonesia, should receive more attention government, increasing the MSME sector and reducing the poverty rate toindicator success development specifically country with income low per capita. One of the obstacles for MSMEs is not having a strategy that cause MSMEs lacking competitiveness compared to with other products. SWOT analysis is another appropriate alternative to help MSMEs determine strategy competition And take decision, a ownerbusinesses must recognize any weaknesses, power, threat, opportunity Which owned his business and recognize competitor advantage that you might have.

Based on statistical data from the Creative Economy Agency, the Indonesian economy is dominated by the culinary, fashion and craft subsectors. Warung Manis Perintis, an MSME operating in the culinary sector, experienced a decline in sales of around 65% in early 2021 following the Covid-19 pandemic. Problems faced include limited human resources, ineffective product distribution, and lack of promotion via social media.

Warung Manis has to compete with similar products at lower prices, making its business development complex. In an era of increasing mobility and connectivity, customers face time constraints and have difficulty focusing on one thing. The high exposure to online and offline information makes customers confused and makes it difficult to distinguish valuable advertisements from those that are not. They prefer to look to trusted sources of advice, such as friends and family. Recommendations and social circle influence have a high value in influencing purchasing decisions. It is important for business owners to build strong relationships with customers and create positive experiences to increase customer trust and loyalty.

This research attempts to create a sales increase plan Which lowered from strategy business MSMEs Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer, so that in its development between need And quality will still support strategy Which executed. Observation in study This is analyze determination strategyfried food business, where in analyzing the determination of fried food business strategy is to use SWOT and QSPM analysis. This is based on research carried out by Akbar, et,al (2022) where the SWOT and QSPM analysis was carried out aim For know factor internal And factor external Which can affect sales of the company's products. Likewise with research by Novita Sari And Samahudi (2021) Where in his research use SWOT(strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities And Threats) And Quantitative strategy planning matrices (QSPM). Study This do planning enhancement sales through SWOT analysis developed by Albert S. Humphrey. Where SWOT Analysis according to Albert S. Humphrey is a conceptual framework Which used For evaluate Strength (Strengths), Weakness (Weaknesses), Opportunity (Opportunities), And Threat (Threats) Which faced byan organization or project. According to Humphrey, a SWOT analysis can helporganizations in formulating effective strategies by considering factor internal And external Which influence performance And success organization.In matter This researcher discuss Factor about environment external And internal UMKM Warung Manis Perintis. So, you will get an identification of strengths (Strength), weakness (Weakness), chance (Opportunity) And threat(Threat). This identification will influence every policy and program increased sales, including in business activities, resource requirements human, sales promotion.

This research is expected to produce an improvement strategy sale For help determine objective Which Can achieved. With planningA good increase in sales will make Warung Manis MSMEs pioneersReady following developments and demands of global change.

Formulation The problem of this research is; 1) How does SWOT analysis determine a sales increase strategy Which right on MSMEs Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer?; 2) How form strategy based on Internal And External Matrix, AndQuantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM) is appropriate to be applied in MSMEs Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer?.

Based on question study, so objective from study This are: 1) For analyze strength, weakness, opportunity And threat from Roadside stallSweet Pioneer; 2) Expected capable produce A strategy business For helpincrease sale Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer. Study This limited by room scope analysis situation internal And external, as well asrepair business strategy Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer in overcome situation moment This.

Study This expected can used as material reference And addition outlook about determination strategy business with method SWOT to determine business strategy in a business. Results study This can made as material input forBusiness Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer Makassar in planning determination business venture strategy culinary. Results study This expected can give contribution And benefitfor business, so that can take decision as well as formulate business strategy using SWOT analysis, so you can used For determine decision sake progress his business.

This research has a conceptual framework which will be explained in the image below and more clear will displayed on next discussion. Framework conceptual under guide study This For find strategy business new For Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer And produce plan action real Which can implemented, Thenstudy study factor internal And external in Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

The approach used in this research is a research approach qualitative. This research means presenting a description of the data obtained through interviews and observations. Therefore, in research reports, the data is stated and analyzed in form results interviews and observation as well as questionnaire. The research was conducted at Warung Manis Perintis, located at Jalan Perintis Independence 4 Lr. 1B No. 12 Makassar.

Source data which used in study this form data primary which researcher get done with do direct observation at the research location, precisely at Warung Manis Pioneer in Makassar and do interview with parties which related in study this. Secondary data in this research is based on written documents obtained from party company. Data secondary this nature internal where information obtained directly from Warung Manis Perintis at Makassar. Researcher use method collection data to respondents with method observation, interview, documentation, and questionnaire after collecting data and answering the problems faced by roadside stall Sweet Pioneer used method analysis which used for solution formulation problem the, such as analysis SWOT, matrix factor strategy internal (IFAS), matrix factor strategy external (EFAS), matrix SWOT, matrix evaluation factor internal external (IE) and Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Analysis Factor Internal

Analysis STP

Analysis segmenting, targeting, positioning (STP) also can applied on MSMEs (Business Micro, Small, and Intermediate) wrong the only one Warung Manis Perintis MSMEs to help them understand the market and develop effective marketing strategies. Here's how application STP on MSMEs:

1. Segmentation (*Segmenting*): Warung Manis Perintis MSMEs chose segment through location geographical MSMEs and focus on segment which located in around the area the. Where MSMEs fried food roadside stall Sweet Pioneer is at in near area House Sick, office, school/college and accommodation..
2. Targeting (*Targeting*): MSMEs Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer can target segment of office workers, hospital employees, students looking for snacks fast serve.
3. Placement (*Positioning*): MSMEs Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer can emphasize the use of packaging in the form of boxes and presentation fried food which still hot nor warm until to consumers as well as affordable prices for their products however this is also a weakness for Warung MSMEs Sweet Pioneers in limited manpower resources nor in matter finance. Besides that change preference customers and consumer trends in food and snacks can changed with fast. MSMEs fried food need still follow these changes and continually update their marketing strategies so that still relevant to customer preferences.

With apply approach STP, MSMEs Roadside stall Sweet Pioneers can better understand their customers, targeting segments which most potency al, and positioning product or brand they better in a competitive market. STP analysis can help MSMEs Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer in develop strategy marketing which more focused and successful.

Analysis Mix Marketing

Philip Kotler define mix marketing as series variable marketing under control which used by company for produce response which controlled company, from market the target, mix marketing consists on all matter which can carried out by the company to influence the demand for its products, which known with "four P", namely product, price, location, and promotion"

a. Product

In mix marketing, product refers on goods and service offered by companies to their target markets. Product which offered very important for brand because is matter which most fundamental to a business. As for type fried food which for sale is fried bananas, breadfruit, fried bananas with using toppings in the form of chocolate and cheese, banana peppe, bakwan, fried otak-otak, cassava, fried nuggets, sweet potatoes, fried meatballs, stuffed tofu, breadfruit, banana tempeh, peppe.

Figure 2. Product Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer

Figure 3 Review Product Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer

Like Which showed by picture in on, customer Warung Manis Perintis is satisfied with the product delivered to consumer. Matter This show that product Which offeredby Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer the suitable For segment market Roadside stallManis The pioneer of this analysis is the product offering by Warung Manis Pioneer produce strength Which is satisfaction customer Because flavor And quality Which in accordance Which sent to customer, Andweakness resulting from is limited energy Work.

b. Price

Price fried food For purchase direct in place norvia WhatsApp (WA) Roadside stall Sweet Sweet range from price 15 Thousand-20 Thousand like Which stated on menu Roadside stall Sweet Pioneerunder This

Figure 3 Menu Roadside stall Sweet

Prices for fried food via the e-commerce application, namely Go-food, Grab Food, And Shopeefood range between 25 Thousand-35 Thousand due to taxes and commissions from that party worth 20% until 35%. According to research conducted by the owner himself, the productcompetitors who offer prices above the price set by the shop sweet. However, Warung Manis Perintis realized that its product offered is different from other places both in terms of packaging Good so that price Which offered Also quite affordable.

c. Place

Warung Manis Perintis produces products in a private home on Jl Perintis Independen 4 Lr.1B No.12. Mr. Saleh chose to use his own house because it was more economical than renting a place. The target market can be reached via chat, telephone and e-commerce applications such as Go-food, Grab Food and Shopeefood. However, the weakness of this place is that it is located in an alley which makes it difficult for buyers to make direct purchases.

Figure 4 Place Sales Roadside stall Sweet

d. Promotion (Promotion)

The role of promotion is to help marketers to communicate information to potential customers. This information can be in the form of the existence of the Product (awareness), the value and benefits the product offers (utility). A well-designed promotional mix is critical to building and positioning a brand. Warung Manis Perintis promotes its products through social media in the form of Instagram, Facebook and WhatsApp.

Figure 5 Media Social Roadside stall Sweet

Besides through media social Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer Also do promotion through word of mouth marketing (information mouthword of mouth) which can be done either directly face to face sales or through online media. From promotional analysis it produces Word Of Mouth Marketing Which become strength they, And Also give rise to weakness that islack of source Power man For handle promotion Good in a waydirect or via social media .

2. Analysis Factor External

In analyzing external factors, companies often apply various analytical methodologies and tools, such as PEST analysis that examines aspects Political, Economy, Social, And Technology, as well as evaluation to competition in industry which is relevant.

a. Analysis Competitor

In analyzing the position and development strategy of Warung Manis Perintis, the benchmarking approach is used as the main tool. The benchmarking process involves internal benchmarking and analysis of how other companies achieve high performance, as explained by Riley in 2012.

In the context of Indonesia's creative industries, MSMEs such as Warung Manis Perintis are experiencing significant growth. Kaku Food and Raja Pisang Kipas Medan Igor were chosen as references because they have similar characteristics to Warung Manis Perintis. Warung Manis Perintis' goal is to emulate and possibly surpass Kaku Food's success by identifying strategies that improve product and service quality, as well as increase customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Next, the discussion will continue on the benchmarking results between Warung Manis Perintis, Kaku Food, and Raja Pisang Kipas Medan Igor with use model business canvas as frameworkthe analysis.

Table 1 . Comparison Model Business

Benchmarking Model Business			
Component	Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer	Rigid Food	Banana King Fan Medan Igor
Segment customer	Customer Business, lover culinary	Lower Culinary, Customer business,	Lower culinary, customer business, Tourist
Proposition Mark	Price affordable, quality tall, food authentic Makassar, variant flavor And innovation	Affordable prices, hours long operational, Highly service and Fast, varied flavors and innovation, flexibility booking, range branch	Affordable prices, hours Long operational, good taste authentic, branch reach
Channel	Shop physique only One, booking on line, platforms delivery food	Physical stores that have Lots branch, booking online, delivery platform food	Physical stores that have many branch, booking on line, platforms delivery food
Connection customer	Bait come back, page Facebook, Instagram,	Program loyalty, bait come back, Instagram, program discount each month	Instagram, Promo every Sunday
Genre income	Sale product	Sale product, Franchise, royalties, influencers	Sale product, Franchise, royalties, influencers
SourceKey	Material standard quality, innovation product, place production only 1	Material standard quality, innovation product, place production There is 7	Material standard quality, product innovation, place production There is 4
ActivityMain	Preparation Raw material, process production, quality and cleanliness, packaging, marketing,	Preparation Material Baku, process production, quality and cleanliness, packaging, marketing, management finance	Preparation Material Baku, process production, quality and cleanliness, packaging, marketing, management finance
PartnerMain	Supplier Material Baku, Media Social	Supplier Material Baku, Media Social, Party Regulations and Certification	Supplier Material Baku, Media Social, Party Regulations and Certification

In determining the benchmark for Warung Manis Perintis, the choice fell on a brand that has proven successful in meeting similar consumer needs. KAKU Food, for example, has emphasized the importance of five main pillars in building a business: finance, product, human resources, marketing, and research and development. This brand also emphasizes the importance of business adaptability to various conditions, by strengthening the digital ecosystem through social media, online ordering systems and digital payment services. KAKU Food's success can be seen from sales reaching hundreds of portions every day, and having seven branches in Makassar. Warung Manis Perintis can learn from KAKU Food's strategy and improve its business adaptability to remain responsive to changes in consumer behavior.

b. Analysis PEST

PEST analysis is the method used to analyze external factors in the business environment. This analysis includes Politics (Political), Economy (Economics), Social (Social), And Technology (Technological).

1). Political

Government Regulation (PP) no. 7 of 2021 concerning Convenience, Protection and Empowerment of Micro, Small and Cooperatives and Enterprises Intermediate. Regulation This covers various aspect like definition MSMEs, criteria, right And obligation, as well as facility Which given government for MSMEs. Convenience and Empowerment of Cooperatives and This PP MSME provides various conveniences and support to cooperative And MSMEs in matter establishment, permits, capital, access to markets, and business development. And also this PP Incubation too regulates the implementation of incubation for cooperatives and MSMEs, which aims to provide assistance, training and facilities support so that cooperatives and MSMEs can develop optimally. From this analysis it can be concluded that generating opportunities from political factors that increase the size of the market, but also yield the threat of more competitors that Warung must face Sweet Pioneer.

2).Economy

Figure 6. Results Survey Economy Creative Year 2020

Source: Bankdata.kememparekraf (2020)

The image above shows the related infographic statistics and resultssurvey of the creative economy in 2020, it appears that in estimation, GDP The nominal ADHB of the creative economy in 2018-2020 experienced a positive trend,although in terms of ADHK GDP growth in 2020 experience growth -2.39%. At number This expected capable give contribution Which significant to growth economy national.

Figure 7. Contribution GDP economy creative according to subsector

Source: Bankdata.kememparekraf (2020)

Based on data statistics Body Economy Creative, economy inIndonesia dominated by 3 sector Which every the year contribute that is culinary Which recorded donate around (42%), Fashion (18%) And Craft(15%). In Sulawesi South Culinary exists in order number 1 subsector Creative Economy that is24.59% And is at in region city Makassar as big as 6.44% Which can seen on picture under This:

Figure 8 Spread perpetrator economy creativeaccording to subsector in South Sulawesi Region

In this case, it is noted that the culinary sector has potential big For Keep going grow every the year. From analysis economy produce opportunity for Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer For request product local more Lots And can happen enhancement sales forRoadside stall Sweet Pioneer.

3).Social

The majority of the population in the fried food business in Tamalanrea Jaya workers and students, then the demand for practical and fried foods affordable maybe high. Where is also the trend in fried MSMEs is provide

variation product Which diverse And unique. Besides traditional fried foods such as tofu, tempeh and bakwan, fried MSMEs Also create innovation with add material- material new, like banana, sweet potato, cassava, or combine various material into one product. This is an opportunity for Warung Manis Perintis For develop better in the future.

4).Technology

Indonesia has a very fast growth in the use of digital technology. Datareportal.com's report "Digital Indonesia 2023" predicts the number of Indonesian internet users will reach 215 million in 2023. The increasing use of mobile devices and demand for digital content is attracting attention and can be an important strategy for marketers and companies in Indonesia. Marketers and businesses are expected to increase their focus on developing innovative and engaging content and using digital technology platforms to reach wider and more engaged audiences. WhatsApp, Instagram, YouTube and Tiktok are the social media most used by Indonesian people, with WhatsApp as a platform that makes it easy for business people to interact with consumers. The Covid-19 pandemic has accelerated the transformation of business and sales from traditional to online, creating an opportunity for Warung Manis Perintis to utilize digital technology platforms in product marketing.

c. Analysis Component SWOT

After all analysis done, interview deep to Father Saleh Muis Dapi as ownerRoadside stall Sweet Pioneers, so results are formed SWOT as follows:

S	W	O	Q
Strengths	Weakness	Opportunities	Threats
Has taste Which authentic The priceaffordable Material quality standard ones quality Yang Food many people like itperson Product varietydiverse Packaging modelWhich interesting Place of businessWhich strategic Social media as means promotion	Production process Which long Dependency to owner Lack of loyalty Employee Marketing Still not enough	Connection Which good with material supplier standard There is supportfrom government Market Which wide Progress Technology	Business competition Which strict Trends Health Rising prices raw materials andSupporter Crisis economy

Picture 5.4 Analysis SWOT

After all external and internal analysis is carried out, it is used for determine *the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities* and *Threats* of Warung Manis The pioneer shown in the image above. This is the main strength for WarungManis Perintis is a strength in terms of products that have an authentic taste with price Which affordable with packaging Which Good compared with productother as well as potency For develop fast in period front. Whereas its weaknessRoadside stall Sweet Pioneer Alone is process production Which Enough long as well asloyalty of human resources for product development. And last The main threat to Warung Manis Perintis is intense competition especially when it comes to prices and health trends.

Matrix IFAS: After processing data questionnaire, so following is displayed resultsanalysis form matrix IFAS.

Table 2. Matrix IFAS

Strength	Weight	Ratings	Score
S1	0.08	3.30	0.26
S2	0.09	3.60	0.31
S3	0.08	3.50	0.29
S4	0.09	3.65	0.32
S5	0.07	2.95	0.21
S6	0.08	3.40	0.28
S7	0.08	3.35	0.27
S8	0.09	3.70	0.33
Total			2.27
Weakness	Weight	Ratings	Score
W1	0.08	3.50	0.29
W2	0.08	3.50	0.29
W3	0.09	3.55	0.30
W4	0.09	3.70	0.33
Total			1.22
Total Whole			3.49

Based on the results of the analysis above, it was found that the total consideration The IFA in this study was 3.49 which, if based on IE principles, this total is in quadrant I. This quadrant shows business conditions that have strong internals and need to be fostered so that they continue maintain the quality. Analysis factor internal This Also very important to help MSME owners in formulating strategies and policy Which appropriate, with utilise strength Which There is And Minimize the impact of weaknesses. This analysis can also be helpful in identify opportunity For growth And repair in periodfront

Matrix EFAS

These external factors include challenges which are: factor positive for company And Threat Which is factor negativefor business the. Factors This obtained from collection data questionnaire based on SWOT analysis.

Table 3. Matrix EFAS

Challenge	Weight	Ratings	Score
O1	0.11	3.25	0.37
O2	0.13	3.80	0.50
O3	0.12	3.45	0.41
O4	0.13	3.70	0.48
Total			1.76
Threat	Weight	Ratings	Score
T1	0.12	3.40	0.40
T2	0.13	3.65	0.46
T3	0.13	3.85	0.52
T4	0.13	3.65	0.46
Total			1.84
Total Whole			3.60

Based on the results of the analysis above, it was found that the total consideration The EFA in this study was 3.60 which, if based on IE principles, this total is in quadrant I. This quadrant shows business conditions that have strong external factors, where this is must be balanced with more organized business development so that this can be achieved face challenges as well see opportunities Which There is.

Analysis IE

Based on the IFAS and EFAS analysis results in this research obtained IE analysis Which made in something matrix as following:

Table 4. Matrix IE

Levels	Strong (3-4): Average (2-3) Weak (1-2)		
	3.49		
High (3-4):	I	II	III
3.60			
Medium (2-3)	IV	V	VI
Low (1-2)	VII	VIII	IX

From results on, obtained that total weighted internal and external are in column/quadrant I. This shows that business conditions, when viewed from internal and external factors, are in conditions of growth and development strategy. Quadrant I is the ideal place to be IE matrix, shows that a company has strength internal Which strong Which in line with opportunity external Which profitable. In conditions for the company's growth and development strategy own strength internal Which makes it possible For chase existing external opportunities. On moment Which The same, condition strategy grow And build Also shows that the company must strengthen its internal strength For reach growth Which sustainable. This highlighting importance investment in enhancement quality, efficiency operational, AndHR development.

Matrix SWOT

Instrument This serve method For combine potency Andrisks from the outside with the internal advantages and disadvantages of the Warung Sweet Pioneer, resulting in four different strategic options. Table 5 show matrix SWOT Which summarize analysis SWOT from study This.

Table 5. Matrix SWOT

<p>INTERNAL</p> <p>EXTERNAL</p>	<p>STRENGTH</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authentic taste • Quality raw materials • An affordable price • Strategic business location • Attractive packaging model • Wide variety of products • Food that is popular with many people • Social media as a promotional tool 	<p>WEAKNESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Long production process ☐ Lack of Employee loyalty ☐ Dependence on the owner ☐ Marketing is still lacking
<p>OPPORTUNITY</p> <p>Good relationship with raw material suppliers There is support from the government Wide market Technological Progress</p>	<p>SO STRATEGY</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Procurement of a variety of flavors and new types of products ▪ Creating collaborations with influencers 	<p>WO STRATEGY</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Carrying out employee training and development ▪ Providing promotions on social media
<p>THREAT</p> <p>Tight business competition Rising prices of raw and supporting materials Economy Crysis Health Trends</p>	<p>STRATEGY ST</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Create attractive packaging 	<p>WT STRATEGY</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Improved employee welfare ▪ Create fair compensation policies for employees ▪ Development of a positive work environment

Table 4 give analysis comprehensive about strength, weakness, opportunity, And threat Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer, as well as how each of these elements can be utilized or overcome through strategy Which Specific. Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer own strength significant like flavor authentic, price Which affordable, And variation food Which popular Lots person, Which Can capitalized For develop new products. Weaknesses such as the production process long And marketing Which Still not enough can overcome with Stage employee training and development and Procurement of promotions in social media. Threats from intense business competition and price fluctuations raw materials can be responded to by creating attractive packaging. Furthermore, will done analysis Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM) For more detailed analyze alternative strategy Which available, possible Roadside stall Sweet Pioneer For weigh choice strategic with more objectively based on assessment quantitative.

Analysis QSPM

Wheelen and Hunger (2012) stated that the formulation process strategy business covers series stages Which done For determine and choose the right strategy to achieve long-term goals long organization. A number of strategy the relevant ones are pursued in business This between other:

- 1). Variation Flavor And Type Products : Offers a unique variety of flavors and types of fried products And different from competitors.
- 2). Appearance And Packaging Which Attractive : Pay attention to the appearance and packaging of the product. Ensure fried food seen interesting And evocative appetite. Packaging being attractive and professional can give a positive impression to customers and make your product more visible special.
- 3). Training And Development Employee : Give training Which appropriate to employees you to increase Skills they in cook, process food, cleanliness and sanitation, and customer service. Make sure they understand standard security food And procedure applicable operations.
- 4). Promotion Through Media Social : Take advantage of it strength media social For promote business.
- 5). Collaboration with Influencers : Look for local influencers or bloggers who have a large audience relevant with product You. invite they For tasting And recommend product Roadside stall Sweet through reviews, posts, or creative content on social media they. Matter This can help increase awareness brand And interesting interest potential customers.
- 6). Policy Compensation : Determine policy compensation Which fair And competitive Foremployee You. Make sure that wages And allowance Which offered in accordance with standard industry And give adequate incentives. Consider providing incentives addition, like bonus performance or allowance food, For motivating employee.
- 7). Enhancement Well-being Employees : Pay attention to the welfare of your employees by providing safe, comfortable and healthy working facilities and environment. Make sure obedience to regulation security And health Work.
- 8). Development Culture Work Which Positive : Wake up culture Work Which positive with promote cooperation, good communication, and team spirit. Push collaboration between employees and teams, and

create an environment Work inclusive and friendly.
 Results calculation US And BAG in in analysis QSPM showed on table following:

Table 5.5.1 Calculation mark US And BAG Internal factors And external

		Alternative Strategy															
		Strateg y 1		Strateg y 2		Strateg y 3		Strateg y 4		Strateg y 5		Strateg y 6		Strateg y 7		Strateg y 8	
Factor	Wei ght	US	B A G	US	B A G	US	B A G	US	B A G	U S	B A G	US	B A G	US	B A G	US	B A G
Strengt h	0.0 8	3. 66	0. 2 9	3.7 0	0. 2 9	2.6 0	0. 21	3. 00	0. 2 4	2. 50	0. 2 0	2. 83	0. 2 2	3.0 0	0. 2 4	2.5 0	0. 2 0
	0.0 9	3. 00	0. 2 6	2.8 4	0. 25	2.3 0	0. 0	2.5 0	0. 2 2	3. 00	0. 2 6	2.1 6	0. 19	3.3 3	0. 2 9	3.3 3	0. 2 9
	0.0 8	2. 66	0. 2 2	1.8 3	0. 15	2.1 0	0. 18	2. 60	0. 2 2	3. 30	0. 2 8	3.3 3	0. 2 8	2.8 3	0. 2 4	2. 83	0. 2 4
	0.0 9	3.5 0	0. 31	2.3 2	0. 2 0	3.5 0	0. 31	2. 80	0. 25	3. 83	0. 3 4	3. 83	0. 3 4	2.6 6	0. 2 3	2. 66	0. 2 3
	0.0 7	3. 30	0. 2 3	2.1 6	0. 15	3.2 0	0. 2 3	3.1 6	0. 2 2	3. 00	0. 21	3. 00	0. 21	3.0 0	0. 21	3. 00	0. 21
	0.0 8	3. 36	0. 27	2.5 0	0. 2 0	1.8 3	0. 15	2. 83	0. 2 3	3. 00	0. 2 4	3. 00	0. 2 4	2.1 6	0. 18	3. 00	0. 2 4
	0.0 8	3. 80	0. 31	2.1 6	0. 17	2.1 6	0. 17	2.5 0	0. 2 0	3. 00	0. 2 4	2.5 0	0. 2 0	2.8 3	0. 3	3. 83	0. 31
	0.0 9	2. 83	0. 2 5	3.8 3	0. 3 4	2.5 0	0. 2 2	3. 83	0. 3 4	2. 83	0. 25	2.5 0	0. 2 2	2.8 3	0. 25	3.3 3	0. 3 0
Weakne ss	0.0 8	3.1 6	0. 27	3.5 0	0. 2 9	3.6 6	0. 31	2.1 0	0. 18	2. 80	0. 2 4	2. 83	0. 2 4	2.1 6	0. 18	2. 60	0. 2 2
	0.0 8	2. 83	0. 2 4	3.3 0	0. 2 8	3. 00	0. 25	3.5 0	0. 2 9	3.1 6	0. 27	2. 66	0. 2 2	3.3 3	0. 2 8	2.3 0	0. 19
	0.0 9	2.5 0	0. 21	3.3 6	0. 2 9	2.6 6	0. 2 3	3. 20	0. 27	2. 83	0. 2 4	3. 00	0. 2 6	3.8 3	0. 3 3	2.1 0	0. 18
	0.0 9	3. 83	0. 3 4	3.8 0	0. 3 4	3.5 0	0. 31	1.8 3	0. 16	2. 50	0. 2 2	3. 00	0. 27	3.0 0	0. 27	3.5 0	0. 31
Opport unity	0.11	2.1 6	0. 2 4	2.5 0	0. 2 8	3. 00	0. 3 4	3.1 6	0. 3 6	2. 60	0. 2 9	3.3 3	0. 3 8	2.5 0	0. 2 8	2. 66	0. 3 0
	0.13	2.5 0	0. 3 3	3.0 0	0. 4 0	2.6 6	0. 3 5	2. 83	0. 3 7	2. 80	0. 3 7	2. 83	0. 3 7	3.0 0	0. 4 0	3. 00	0. 4 0
	0.12	2.1 6	0. 2 6	3.3 0	0. 4 0	3.5 0	0. 4 2	2.5 0	0. 3 0	3.1 6	0. 3 8	2. 66	0. 3 2	3.3 0	0. 4 0	2.1 6	0. 2 6
	0.13	3. 83	0. 4 9	3.8 3	0. 4 9	3.3 0	0. 4 2	2. 83	0. 3 6	2. 83	0. 3 6	3. 00	0. 3 9	3.8 3	0. 4 9	2. 83	0. 3 6
Threat	0.12	3. 30	0. 3 9	3.0 0	0. 35	2. 84	0. 3 4	2. 60	0. 31	3. 50	0. 41	3.3 0	0. 3 9	2.8 0	0. 3 3	2. 60	0. 31
	0.13	3. 36	0. 4 3	2.6 6	0. 3 4	1.8 3	0. 2 3	2. 80	0. 3 6	3. 30	0. 4 2	3. 83	0. 4 9	3.1 6	0. 4 0	2. 80	0. 3 6
	0.13	3. 80	0. 51	3.5 0	0. 47	2.3 2	0. 31	3.1 6	0. 4 2	3. 36	0. 4 5	3. 00	0. 4 0	2.8 3	0. 3 8	3.1 6	0. 4 2
	0.13	2. 83	0. 3 3	3.8 3	0. 4	2.1 6	0. 27	2. 83	0. 3	3. 80	0. 4	3. 00	0. 3	2.5 0	0. 3	2. 83	0. 3

			6		9				6		8		8		2		6
Total	2.00	62.37	6.21	60.92	6.17	54.62	5.44	56.56	5.66	61.10	6.15	59.59	6.00	58.88	5.91	57.02	5.68

Results Election strategy Which obtained along with the ranking can seen on table following:

Table 5.5.2 Ranking of Alternative Business Strategies in the MSME Warung Fried Food Business Sweet Pioneer

No	Alternative Strategy	Score BAG	Rating
1	Procurement variation flavor And new product types	6.21	1
2	Make packaging Which interesting	6.17	2
3	Procurement promotion in social media	5.44	8
4	Create collaboration with influencers	5.66	7
5	Carrying out training and development employee	6.15	3
6	Create policy compensation Which fair for employee	6.00	4
7	Enhancement well-being employee	5.91	5
8	Development environment Work Which positive	5.68	6

Based on results calculation BAG on analysis QSPM, obtained alternative First the most prioritized is the procurement of a variety of flavors and new types of products with scores BAG as big as 6.21 next with make packaging Which interesting with score BAG 6.17, Then stage training And development employee with score BAG 6.15, furthermore strategy fourth is create policy compensation Which fair for employees with a TAS score of 6.00 then strategies to improve employee welfare, development environment Work Which positive, create collaboration with influencers as well as The least priority strategy is providing social media promotion with TAS scores in a way sequentially are 5.91, 5.68, 5.66, and 5.44.

CONCLUSION

Based on research involving literature studies, discussions in forums, and consulting with experts, the author has analyzed internal factors and external factors that affect the business of Warung Manis Perintis. Found 8 powers (flavor Which authentic, material standard Which quality, Price affordable, strategic location, attractive packaging, variety various products, food that is popular with many people, and social media as means promotion), 4 weakness (production high long, Not enough loyalty, Dependence on owners, and Weak Marketing), 4 opportunities (good relationships with raw material suppliers, support from government, Market Which wide, and Progress technology) and 4 threats (tight business competition, rising prices of raw and supporting materials, Economic crisis, and Health Trends) identified in the SWOT analysis. In conclusion, these strategies are expected to be successful facilitate the implementation of new business models that will help Warung Manis Pioneer in develop his business more carry on analysis Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM) For more detailed analyze alternative strategy Which available, allowing Warung Manis Perintis to weigh strategic options with more objective based on quantitative assessment. Based on data processing and analysis, conclusions regarding form of strategy appropriate marketing to increase sales at the Warung Sweet Pioneer as following; 1) Procurement variation flavor and type product new; 2) Create packaging Which interesting; 3) Procurement promotion in social media; 4) Create collaboration with influencer, 5) Hold training And development employees, 6) Create policy compensation Which fair for employees; 7) Improvement well-being employee; 8) Development environment Work Which positive.

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